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FACTORS AFFECTING JOB SATISFACTION OF LECTURERS AT UNIVERSITY OF TRANSPORT TECHNOLOGY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN VIETNAM

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to identify the factors affecting job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation. The results showed that 4 factors including: Perceived organizational support, Autonomy, Digital transformation and Person - organization fit had a positive and statistically significant impact on the job satisfaction of lecturers. In which, the impact of Perceived organizational support is 22.9%, autonomy is 16%, digital transformation is 35% and Person - organization fit is 21.2% On that basis, the study proposes a number of management solutions to improve the satisfaction level of lecturers in the University of Transport Technology contributing to improving the quality of higher education in the context of digital transformation.

KEYWORDS: Autonomy, Digital Transformation, Job Satisfaction, Perceived Organizational Support, Person-Organization Fit.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation is a global trend that promotes socio-economic development and brings far-reaching changes in all fields, especially higher education. Digital transformation integrates technology into all organizational activities to change the way it operates, improve work efficiency, and create new values (Shwedeh *et al.*, 2023). In recent years, digital transformation in higher education institutions has made significant progress, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic – a time that emphasizes the importance of online learning (Tran, 2023). Digital transformation in higher education is the process of applying digital technology to teaching, research and school administration activities, in order to improve the efficiency and quality of training. In the context that digital universities are becoming a global trend, many studies have raised questions about the impact of this process on the teaching staff. They are the ones who directly carry out educational activities. One of the important aspects of concern is the relationship between digital transformation and job satisfaction of lecturers.

The University of Transport Technology is one of the schools in the Northern region that has achieved many achievements in training quality human resources for society. The university has also made important contributions in providing quality human resources, promoting economic restructuring, political stability, social order and safety, and at the same time linking the interests of the university with social benefits. Over the years, the University has implemented strong digital transformation. The digital transformation process at the University of Transport Technology is having a profound impact on the teaching staff. This is the force that determines the quality of training. Accordingly, lecturers not only face pressure to change technology, but are also influenced by factors such as digital infrastructure, training policies, technical support, organizational culture and personal competence. In addition, faculty job satisfaction is also an important factor affecting teaching quality, productivity, organizational engagement, and willingness to adapt to innovation. Therefore, studying the factors affecting the job satisfaction of lecturers of the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation not only helps to identify the influencing factors in the new environment but also provides a scientific basis for human resource policy making, develop team capacity and promote the effectiveness of digital transformation in schools. Moreover, based on the theoretical model combined with the practical survey at the University of Transport Technology,

the research will contribute to providing concrete empirical evidence, helping school leaders assess the current situation and come up with appropriate solutions to improve the level of satisfaction, create motivation to work and retain lecturers in the long term. This is especially significant in the context of competition among higher education institutions and the increasing requirement to improve the quality of training.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. *Materials*

The relationship between perceived organizational support and job satisfaction

Porter *et al.* (1974) argues that job satisfaction is a person's response to the work and organization in which they work. Dawis & Lofquist (1984) defines job satisfaction as the result of considering the extent to which the work environment meets the individual needs of workers. According to Spector (1997), job satisfaction reflects the degree to which an individual perceives a job that meets their personal needs, desires, and values. Satisfaction levels not only affect attitudes and behaviors in the workplace but are also closely related to productivity, work efficiency, and long-term engagement with the organization. In the higher education environment, especially in the context of today's digital transformation, the job satisfaction of lecturers has become even more important, because this is a factor that directly affects the quality of teaching, research and sustainable development of educational institutions. Overall, job satisfaction is simply the degree to which people love their work and the factors associated with their work. Perceived organizational support refers to the employee's perception that the organization appreciates their contributions and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger *et al.*, 1986). According to Social Exchange Theory, when employees feel supported and valued by the organization, they will respond with a positive attitude and commitment to work. Previous studies (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002) have confirmed that perceived organizational support has a significant effect on job satisfaction, especially in highly professional settings such as higher education.

Numerous international studies have confirmed that perceived organizational support has a positive impact on faculty job satisfaction. Research by Barkhuizen & Rothmann (2008) at South African universities shows that organizational support not only directly affects job satisfaction but also indirectly impacts through improved perceptions of fairness, reduced burnout and increased engagement

with the organization. Another study by Tüzün & Kalemci (2012) in Turkey also demonstrated that when lecturers feel supported by the organization, they tend to be more satisfied with their current work and motivated to continue contributing. In addition, studies by Yoon & Thye (2002) and Ahmad & Yekta (2010) emphasize the mediating role of organizational commitment and support from middle leadership in the relationship between organizational support and satisfaction.

In Vietnam, this relationship has also been clarified through a number of studies in the context of higher education. Research by Nguyen (2019) at public universities in the North shows that perceived organizational support (including professional development support, a friendly working environment, and reasonable remuneration policies) has a significant positive effect on lecturers' job satisfaction. Similarly, Le et al. (2021) when researching at local universities have shown that organizational support plays an important role in improving satisfaction through a sense of respect and recognition within the organization. Another study by Tran (2022) highlights that supportive factor from faculty leaders, such as reasonable work assignments, facilitating research and career development, play a key role in maintaining high levels of satisfaction among young lecturers.

Therefore, the study proposes the hypothesis:

H1: Perceived organizational support has a positive effect on faculty job satisfaction.

The relationship between work autonomy and job satisfaction

Autonomy is a core component of the Self-Determination Theory developed by Deci and Ryan (2000). Accordingly, when individuals have control and decision-making in their work, they will have a stronger intrinsic motivation, thereby improving their sense of satisfaction. For lecturers, being autonomous in designing teaching content, pedagogical methods and scientific research will create conditions to promote their capacity and creativity, thereby increasing career satisfaction. Research by Houston, Meyer and Paewai (2006) at universities in New Zealand shows that lecturers who perceive a high level of autonomy in teaching, research and professional development have significantly higher levels of job satisfaction. Similarly, research by Runhaar, Sanders and Yang (2010) in the Netherlands shows that autonomy in subject design, teaching methods and time allocation are determinants of lecturers' job satisfaction, especially in the context of rapid changes in modern higher education.

In Vietnam, a number of studies have also addressed this relationship in the context of higher education. Research by Nguyen (2017) at public universities in the Central region shows that the level of autonomy in teaching, research and other professional activities is positively correlated with the job satisfaction of lecturers. Another study by Tran (2021) at non-public universities also noted that autonomy is an important motivating factor, helping lecturers feel trusted and recognized, thereby improving satisfaction and commitment to the organization. However, this study also shows that autonomy needs to be accompanied by clear accountability and a supportive work environment, otherwise it will cause stress and a sense of isolation.

From the above theoretical basis, the study proposes the following hypotheses:

H2: Autonomy has a positive effect on the job satisfaction of lecturers.

The relationship between digital transformation and job satisfaction

Digital transformation in higher education is the process of integrating digital technology into teaching, research and management activities to improve quality, efficiency and learner experience. According to Wang & Beynon-Davies (2020), digital transformation brings opportunities to improve work efficiency, flexibility, and quick access to information, thereby contributing to improving job satisfaction of lecturers. In particular, in the post-Covid-19 context, the application of technology to online teaching, academic management and research collaboration has become popular and plays an important role in maintaining the effectiveness of professional work.

Research by Rasheed et al. (2021) highlights that when lecturers are adequately trained and have the opportunity to master digital technology, they feel more confident and satisfied with their teaching roles. In addition, research by Bond et al. (2022) at European universities in the post-COVID-19 era shows that digital transformation helps increase flexibility, improve teaching experience, and enhance faculty career satisfaction, especially in blended learning and blended teaching models.

In Vietnam, the relationship between digital transformation and lecturers' job satisfaction has also been mentioned in a number of recent works. Le (2021) research shows that the level of technology application in teaching, especially through LMS (Learning Management System) systems, has a positive effect on lecturer satisfaction if accompanied by technical support and incentive policies from the school. Similarly, Pham (2022) found that the job

satisfaction of lecturers at regional universities in the context of digital transformation depends heavily on whether the organization provides enough resources, training, and learning opportunities to adapt to technology. However, there are also studies that record a negative trend. For example, Tran (2023) warns that without synchronous preparation and investment, digital transformation can increase work pressure, make lecturers feel overwhelmed, and reduce satisfaction levels.

From there, the study hypothesizes

H3: The level of digital transformation at work has a positive effect on the job satisfaction of lecturers.

The relationship between person - organization fit and job satisfaction

Person-Organization Fit is the degree of similarity between personal values, beliefs, and goals with the culture and orientation of the organization. According to research by Cable and DeRue (2002), this fit not only helps reduce conflict at work but also increases engagement and job satisfaction. In the higher education environment, when lecturers feel that the organization shares the same value system of education, research and sustainable development, they will tend to work more actively and long-term.

In the context of higher education, many studies have shown that person-organization fit is an important factor affecting the professional experience of lecturers. Research by Vandenberghe (1999) at European universities shows that value compatibility between lecturers and educational institutions contributes to the creation of a positive

work environment, reduced stress, and increased satisfaction. Similarly, research by Erdogan, Kraimer and Liden (2004) has demonstrated that person-organization fit helps increase intrinsic motivation, especially when lecturers feel the consistency between their individual academic orientation and the school's educational strategy and philosophy.

In Vietnam, this relationship has also begun to be of interest to researchers in recent years. Tran (2018) research at public universities in the Central region has shown that when lecturers feel that their personal values (such as the spirit of service, academic freedom, dedication to the community) are in line with the university's development orientation, they tend to be more satisfied with their work actively participating in research and long-term engagement. Nguyen's (2021) research at some non-public universities also shows that person-organization fit has a strong impact on satisfaction, especially in the context that universities are under competitive pressure and require rapid innovation. In addition, factors such as support from management, fair evaluation mechanisms and a democratic working environment are identified as conditions that increase the effectiveness of person - organization fit for job satisfaction.

On that basis, the study proposes the hypothesis:

H4: The alignment between person - organization fit has a positive effect on the job satisfaction of lecturers.

Based on the developed hypotheses, the author proposes a research model as follows

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework.

The study variables measured using the 5-point Likert scale are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables in the Model.

Encode	Item	Source
HT1	The university cares about my well-being	Eisenberger et al., 1986
HT2	I get the support I need from the leadership	
HT3	The university appreciates my contributions	
HT4	The university values my satisfaction	
TC1	I have the right to make my own decisions in teaching	Deci & Ryan, 2000
TC2	I have the freedom to be creative in my teaching career	
TC3	I feel the work reflects my personal worth	
TC4	I'm encouraged to suggest my own way of doing things	
CDS1	I am fully equipped with tools and software for online and hybrid teaching	Wang et al., 2020
CDS2	I use learning management platforms (such as Moodle, Google Classroom, etc.) effectively in the teaching process	
CDS3	The application of digital transformation helps me improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching	
CDS4	The use of digital technology helps me save time and effort in professional activities	
GT1	My values align with our values	Cable & Derue, 2002
GT2	The university and I share the same goals and vision	
GT3	I feel like I fit in with the work environment	
HL1	I'm satisfied with my current job	Spector, 1997
HL2	My current job meets my expectations	
HL3	I feel like I want to stay and want to continue working at the University	

2.2. Methods

This study uses a survey design. The survey aims to provide information about the attitudes or views of a group of lecturers of the University of Transport Technology. Furthermore, survey research is a popular research method in the social sciences and humanities. This method allows for quick and effective access to the target group directly related to the research topic, especially in conditions of time and resource constraints. At the same time, collecting data from lecturers who are willing to participate in the survey helps ensure a high response rate and the quality of information obtained, in line with the goal of exploring the factors that affect lecturers' job satisfaction in the context of digital transformation. However, the convenient sampling method limits the ability to generalize research results for the entire teaching staff. This is also a limitation of the study.

Therefore, in the future, the study may apply probabilistic sampling methods or expand the scope of the survey to improve the generality of the results.

In this study, the authors took samples according to a convenient sampling method. The survey participants are lecturers. According to Hair et al. (2010), for exploratory factor analysis, the minimum sample size should be at least 5 times the observed variables. In this study, the author had 18 observed variables, so the minimum sample was 90. After the survey period, the author received 175 valid votes. Thus, the study sample is 175, which is larger than the minimum sample size of 90, ensuring the representativeness of the sample. In which, male lecturers are 109 votes (accounting for 62.3%), female lecturers are 88 votes (accounting for 37.7%), lecturers under 35 years old are 117 votes (accounting for 66.9%), lecturers over 35 years old are 58 votes (accounting for 33.1%).

The random method used is based on the fact that the lecturer is working at the University of Transportation Technology. The questionnaire is sent to the identified respondents. To achieve the most reliable results, the study distributed all face-to-face and online questionnaires to lecturers in the University of Transport Technology in May and June 2025

Survey questionnaires are used to collect data. The questionnaire is designed according to strict guidelines for drafting survey questions and is built according to standards that comply with the requirements (Schutt, 2012). The questionnaire focuses on the lecturers' comments on the factors affecting the job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Transport Technology. Factors measured through the 5-level Likert measurement: (1) – Completely disagree; (2) – Disagree; (3) – No opinion; (4) – Agree; (5) – Completely agree

The questionnaires were tested to detect special defects. This process is carried out outside the study area through a group of lecturers with sample standards similar to the study. The answers have been tested using the Alpha Chronbach measurement for the purpose of improving reliability.

The data was carried out through basic analyses such as statistics, Cronbach's alpha reliability assessment, EFA factor analysis, and linear regression from the collected data through a survey of 175 lecturers working at the University of Transport Technology.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Assessment

The reliability test results of the scale are shown in Table 2. The reliability of the observed variables on the HT, TC, CDS, and TC scales has a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient > 0.6; The total variable correlation

coefficient of the observed variables in HT, TC, CDS and TC > 0.3, thus, these scales are satisfactory for further analysis in the following steps.

Table 2: Quality test results of scales using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient.

No	Item	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Scale Mean if Item Deleted
1	HT1	10.14	3.636	.595	.764	.803
2	HT2	10.09	3.424	.604	.760	
3	HT3	10.04	3.429	.634	.744	
4	HT4	10.14	3.342	.635	.744	
5	TC1	10.31	3.180	.683	.803	.844
6	TC2	10.38	3.548	.659	.812	
7	TC3	10.42	3.336	.681	.802	
8	TC4	10.39	3.459	.704	.793	
9	CDS1	10.18	4.434	.673	.919	.905
10	CDS2	10.19	4.257	.774	.882	
11	CDS3	10.14	4.280	.835	.860	
12	CDS4	10.18	4.147	.876	.845	
13	GT1	6.77	1.583	.570	.659	.744
14	GT2	6.75	1.569	.625	.594	
15	GT3	6.74	1.701	.516	.720	

3.2. EFA Factor Analysis

After testing the reliability of the 15 scales, the

study conducted an exploratory factor analysis with the 15 scales mentioned above

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.817
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1319.790
	df	105
	Sig.	.000

(Source: Results extracted from SPSS software)

Table 4: Total Variance Explained.

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.281	35.208	35.208	5.281	35.208	35.208	3.081	20.542	20.542
2	1.968	13.121	48.328	1.968	13.121	48.328	2.768	18.450	38.992
3	1.803	12.023	60.351	1.803	12.023	60.351	2.555	17.033	56.026
4	1.460	9.732	70.083	1.460	9.732	70.083	2.109	14.057	70.083
5	.782	5.213	75.296						
6	.604	4.024	79.320						
7	.474	3.158	82.477						
8	.463	3.087	85.565						
9	.438	2.922	88.487						
10	.392	2.616	91.103						
11	.379	2.525	93.628						
12	.363	2.420	96.048						
13	.265	1.764	97.812						
14	.234	1.560	99.373						
15	.094	.627	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
(Source: Results extracted from SPSS software)

The results of KMO = 0.817 > 0.5, sig Bartlett's Test = 0.000 < 0.05 indicate that the EFA discovery factor

analysis is appropriate. Perform factor analysis by Principal components with Varimax rotation. The

results of Table 4 show that there are 4 factors cited based on the Eigenvalues criterion greater than 1. Thus, these 4 factors best summarize the information of the 15 observed variables included in EFA or can be understood as the 15 initial observed variables grouped into 4 groups. The total variance extracted by these 4 factors is 70.083% >50%. Thus, the 4 factors cited explained 70.083% of the data variation of the 15 observed variables involved in EFA.

Table 5 presents the matrix of rotated factors as follows.

Table 5: Rotated Component Matrixa.

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
CDS4	.908			
CDS3	.881			
CDS2	.839			
CDS1	.705			
TC4		.845		
TC2		.806		
TC3		.775		
TC1		.768		
HT3			.811	
HT2			.781	
HT4			.776	
HT1			.713	
GT2				.843
GT1				.796
GT3				.721
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.				
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.				
a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.				
(Source: Results extracted from SPSS software)				

The results of the group of factors are as follows
 Group 1: includes variables CDS4 (The use of digital technology helps me save time and effort in professional activities), CDS3 (The application of digital transformation helps me improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching), CDS2 (I use learning management platforms (such as Moodle, Google Classroom, etc.) effectively in the teaching process),

CDS1 (I am fully equipped with tools and software for online and hybrid teaching) (factor load factor from 0.705 to 0.908) is called digital transformation.

Group 2: including the variables TC4 (I'm encouraged to suggest my own way of doing things), TC2 (I have the freedom to be creative in my teaching career), TC3 (I feel the work reflects my personal worth), TC1 (I have the right to make my own decisions in teaching) (factor load factor from 0.768 to 0.845) called autonomy

Group 3: including HT3 (The university appreciates my contributions), HT2 (I get the support I need from the leadership), HT4 (The university values my satisfaction), HT1 (The university cares about my well-being) (factor load factor from 0.713 to 0.811) called perceived organizational support

Group 4: including the variables GT2 (The university and I share the same goals and vision), GT1 (My values align with our values), GT3 (I feel like I fit in with the work environment) (factor load factor from 0.721 to 0.843) called Person - Organization Fit

3.3. Linear Regression Models

According to Table 6 data, the value of R² = 0.460 shows that the regression model explains 46.0% of the variation of the dependent variable (the level of satisfaction in the work of lecturers) through 4 independent variables: perceived organizational support, autonomy, digital transformation, and person - organization fit. This reflects that the model has a fairly good level of explanation in the context of social research. A corrected R² value = 0.448 indicates that the model still maintains its relevance when adjusted by the number of variables, avoiding overestimation due to adding more variables to the model. The Durbin-Watson index of the research model = 1.998~2, so the model has no autocorrelation phenomenon

Table 6: Results of Multiple Regression Analysis.

Model Summary ^b										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.678 ^a	.460	.448	.55024	.460	36.247	4	170	.000	1.998
a. Predictors: (Constant), GT, HT, TC, CDS										
b. Dependent Variable: HL										
(Source: Results extracted from SPSS software)										

The results of the inspection of the significance level shown in Table 7 are as follows

Table 7: ANOVAa Analysis Results.

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.

1	Regression	43.898	4	10.974	36.247	.000 ^b
	Residual	51.470	170	.303		
	Total	95.368	174			
a. Dependent Variable: HL						
b. Predictors: (Constant), GT, HT, TC, CDS						
(Source: Results extracted from SPSS software)						

The value of $F = 36.247$ with $Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the model given is in line with the actual data. In other words, the variables GT, HT, TC, CDS have a linear correlation with the HL

variable with 95% reliability. The results of the analysis of the regression coefficients of the model are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Regression of the Model.

Coefficients ^a											
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.456	.344		-1.327	.186					
	HT	.282	.076	.229	3.704	.000	.446	.273	.209	.834	1.199
	TC	.198	.079	.160	2.523	.013	.423	.190	.142	.790	1.266
	CDS	.381	.075	.350	5.105	.000	.583	.365	.288	.676	1.478
	GT	.262	.075	.212	3.508	.001	.410	.260	.198	.873	1.146
a. Dependent Variable: HL											

The results show that the variables HT, TC, CDS and GT have a value of $Sig. < 0.05$, so these variables are meaningfully correlated with lecturers' job satisfaction with 95% reliability. According to Table 8, the independent variables all have a < 2 coefficient of variance magnification, no multilinearity. Multiple linear regression analysis to examine the impact of factors on job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation. The regression results show that the variables of perceived organizational support, autonomy, digital transformation, and person - organization fit all have a positive impact on the job satisfaction of lecturers. From the analysis results, the regression equation estimates the factors affecting job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation as follows:

$$HL = 0.282*HT + 0.198*TC + 0.381*CDS + 0.262*GT - 0.456 + \epsilon$$

The regression equation shows that perceived organizational support, autonomy, digital transformation, and person - organization fit all have a positive impact on lecturers' job satisfaction. First of all, perceived organizational support has a positive impact on faculty job satisfaction. This positive effect is also the conclusion of the study by Eisenberger et al. (1986), Tüzün & Kalemci (2012), Le et al. (2021), Tran (2022). Autonomy also has a positive impact. The results of this study are consistent with those of

Deci & Ryan, 2000, Runhaar, Sanders and Yang (2010), Tran (2021). Digital Transformation has a positive impact on faculty job satisfaction. Wang et al., (2020), Bond et al. (2022), Pham (2022), Tran (2023) also came to a similar conclusion about the positive impact of digital transformation on lecturers' job satisfaction. Finally, Person - Organization Fit also has a positive impact. This is also the result of research by Cable & Derue, 2002, Erdogan, Kraimer and Liden (2004), Nguyen's (2021). The results of this study show that the conclusions are similar to the results of domestic and foreign research. However, due to differences in demographics and the digital transformation context of the University of Transportation Technology, the positive impact of this study may have insignificant deviations from previous studies. The job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation will increase if this factor is satisfied. Therefore, in order to improve the job satisfaction of lecturers of the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation, these factors need to be improved even more. The Beta value indicates the importance of the independent variable to the dependent variable. Table 8 shows the degree of influence between the 4 independent and dependent variables. Among the variables, the impact of perceived organizational support variable (HT) was 22.9%, autonomy (TC) was 16%, digital transformation (CDS) was 35% and person - organization fit (GT)

was 21.2%

4. CONCLUSION

The research results show that there are 4 factors that positively and statistically affect the job satisfaction of lecturers at the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation. In order to improve the job satisfaction of lecturers of the University of Transport Technology in the context of digital transformation in the coming time, the University needs to focus on a number of solutions as follows:

Firstly, it is necessary to promote the harmony of values between individual lecturers and the development orientation of the organization, through internal communication, building a positive and consistent organizational culture.

Alignment of personal and organizational values is the factor that has the strongest impact on public satisfaction. To strengthen this harmony, the University needs to clarify the core values in internal communication, integrate those values into professional activities as well as team development. In addition, it is recommended to organize activities to build a positive culture such as seminars to share values, orient new lecturers or reflect organizational values through commendation and evaluation activities. Consistency between the words and actions of leaders also plays an important role in spreading organizational values effectively.

Secondly, it is necessary to strengthen activities that show support from the organization for lecturers, such as: professional support, welfare policies, friendly working environment and attention to the personal development needs of lecturers. Specifically, the university needs to develop and improve welfare policies in accordance with the characteristics of teaching work such as reward regimes, professional support, research subsidies, etc. This helps lecturers feel an interest in the quality of life and long-term career. In addition, leaders at all levels in the university need to actively approach, listen and support lecturers in academic and administrative activities. A positive relationship between leaders and lecturers not only improves

work efficiency but also strengthens organizational trust.

On the other hand, the university needs to have a mechanism to evaluate and recognize the contributions of lecturers in a timely, transparent and fair manner. Recognizing achievements helps faculty feel more respected and engaged with the organization. In addition, the University should periodically organize internal surveys, sharing forums or exchanges between the Board of Directors and lecturers to receive feedback, thereby adjusting policies in accordance with actual needs.

Thirdly, the University needs to continue to invest in and improve the quality of digital transformation activities, especially technology infrastructure, digital skills training and technology application in teaching to support lecturers to work more effectively and be more satisfied in the digital environment. In the context of digital universities, the application of technology not only supports work efficiency but also contributes to improving the professional experience of lecturers. The positive results show that the University is on the right track, but it is necessary to continue to promote comprehensive digital transformation strategies. Specifically, it is necessary to invest in upgrading technology infrastructure (smart classrooms, stable learning management platform - LMS), organize digital skills training programs and encourage innovation through online tools. At the same time, the technical support department should operate more effectively and proactively in supporting lecturers, especially those who are not yet tech-savvy.

Fourth, the University should empower and create conditions for lecturers to show autonomy in their work. Autonomy in lesson design and choice of teaching methods will promote creativity and increase satisfaction. The university also needs to review the process of managing lecturers to ensure that professional initiative is not limited by overly rigid administrative regulations. In addition, it is necessary to encourage innovative forms of teaching, flexibly evaluate learning outcomes, and support modern learning models such as blended learning.

Conflict of Interest: Authors should disclose any financial or personal ties, in the manuscript, that could be perceived as inappropriately biasing their work.

REFERENCES

- Agustin, F., Suherdi, D., Ahmad, K. Z., & Yekta, Z. A. (2010). Relationship between perceived organizational support, leadership behavior, and job satisfaction: An empirical study in Iranian organizations. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 2(2), 14–22.

- Al-Fraihat, D., Joy, M., Masa'deh, R., & Sinclair, J. (2020). Evaluating e-learning systems success: An empirical study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 102, 67–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.08.004>
- Barkhuizen, N., & Rothmann, S. (2008). Occupational stress of academic staff in South African higher education institutions. *South African Journal of Psychology*, 38(2), 321–336. <https://doi.org/10.1177/008124630803800205>
- Bond, M., Bedenlier, S., Marín, V. I., & Händel, M. (2022). Emergency remote teaching in higher education: Mapping the first global online semester. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 19(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-021-00282-x>
- Cable, D. M., & DeRue, D. S. (2002). The convergent and discriminant validity of subjective fit perceptions. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(5), 875–884. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.87.5.875>
- Dawis, R. V., & Lofquist, L. H. (1984). *A psychological theory of work adjustment: An individual-differences model and its applications*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(3), 500–507. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.500>
- Erdogan, B., Kraimer, M. L., & Liden, R. C. (2004). Work value congruence and intrinsic career success: The compensatory roles of leader–member exchange and perceived organizational support. *Personnel Psychology*, 57(2), 305–332. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2004.tb02493.x>
- Hoang, C. G., Tran, T. H. L., & Mac, M. D. T. (2023). Digital transformation in higher education institutions through the lens of the digital maturity model: A case study at University of Economics and Law. *Journal of Science and Technology Development – Economics-Law and Management*, 7(2), 4355–4370. <https://doi.org/10.32508/stdjelm.v7i2.1199>
- Houston, D., Meyer, L. H., & Paewai, S. (2006). Academic staff workloads and job satisfaction: Expectations and values in academe. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 28(1), 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600800500283734>
- Kristof, A. L. (1996). Person–Organization fit: An integrative review of its conceptualizations, measurement, and implications. *Personnel Psychology*, 49(1), 1–49. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1996.tb01790.x>
- Le, T. M. N., et al. (2021). The influence of organizational support on job satisfaction of university lecturers. *Journal of Science and Technology – The University of Danang*, 19(3), 45–52.
- Le, V. H., & Nguyen, T. H. (2021). The impact of digital transformation on job satisfaction of university lecturers in Vietnam. *Vinh University Journal of Science*, 50(2), 23–30.
- Nguyen, T. T. H. (2017). The relationship between job autonomy and career satisfaction among public university lecturers. *Hue University Journal of Science: Social Sciences and Humanities*, 126(6), 89–96.
- Nguyen, T. T. H. (2019). Organizational support and job satisfaction of lecturers in public universities in Northern Vietnam. *VNU Journal of Science: Economics and Business*, 35(2), 112–120.
- Nguyen, V. T., & Pham, T. H. (2021). Person–Organization value fit and job satisfaction of lecturers in non-public universities. *Ho Chi Minh City Open University Journal of Science*, 16(2), 112–123.
- Pham, T. M., & Tran, Q. B. (2022). Job satisfaction of university lecturers in the context of digital transformation: A case study at regional universities. *Vietnam Journal of Educational Sciences*, 18(4), 55–63.
- Rasheed, R. A., Kamsin, A., & Abdullah, N. A. (2021). Challenges in the online learning environment during the COVID-19 pandemic – A systematic review. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 4, 100103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2021.100103>
- Rhoades, L., & Eisenberger, R. (2002). Perceived organizational support: A review of the literature. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(4), 698–714. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.87.4.698>
- Riggle, R. J., Edmondson, D. R., & Hansen, J. D. (2009). A meta-analysis of the relationship between perceived organizational support and job outcomes: 20 years of research. *Journal of Business Research*, 62(10), 1027–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2008.05.003>
- Runhaar, P., Sanders, K., & Yang, H. (2010). Stimulating teachers' reflection and feedback asking: An interplay of self-efficacy, learning goal orientation, and transformational leadership. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(5), 1154–1161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2009.12.001>
- Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59, 603.

- Shwede, F., Aburayya, A., & Mansour, M. (2023). The impact of organizational digital transformation on employee performance: A study in the UAE. *Migration Letters*, 20(S10), 1260–1274.
<https://doi.org/10.59670/ml.v20iS10.5710>
- Spector, P. E. (1997). *Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences*. Sage Publications.
- Tran, T. H. N. (2018). The relationship between person–organization value fit and job satisfaction of lecturers: A study at public universities in Central Vietnam. *Journal of Science and Education*, 38(5), 87–94.
- Tran, T. K. L. (2023). The dual impact of digital transformation on job satisfaction among university lecturers. *Journal of Educational Management*, 25(1), 41–49.
- Tran, V. D. (2022). The role of faculty leadership in job satisfaction of young lecturers. *Journal of Science – Hanoi National University of Education*, 67(5), 37–45.
- Tran, V. L., & Colleagues. (2021). The impact of job autonomy on job satisfaction of lecturers in non-public universities in Vietnam. *Journal of Economic Development – University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City*, 32(3), 57–68.
- Tüzün, I. K., & Kalemci, R. A. (2012). Organizational and supervisory support in relation to employee turnover intentions. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 27(5), 518–534.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02683941211235418>
- Vandenberghe, C. (1999). Organizational culture, person–culture fit, and turnover: A replication in the healthcare industry. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 20(2), 175–184.
[https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1379\(199903\)20:2<175::AID-JOB882>3.0.CO;2-E](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1379(199903)20:2<175::AID-JOB882>3.0.CO;2-E)
- Wang, Y., Han, H., & Beynon-Davies, P. (2020). Understanding the adoption of digital transformation: A dynamic capability approach. *Information Systems Journal*, 30(4), 759–787.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12283>
- Yoon, J., & Thye, S. R. (2002). A dual process model of organizational commitment: Job satisfaction and organizational support. *Work and Occupations*, 29(1), 97–124.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0730888402029001005>